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Positive-end expiratory pressure reduces incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia in nonhypoxemic patients*

Manzano, Francisco MD; Fernández-Mondéjar, Enrique MD, PhD; Colmenero, Manuel MD; Poyatos, María Eugenia MD; Rivera, Ricardo MD; Machado, Juan MD; Catalán, Iñaki MD; Artigas, Antonio MD, PhD

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